

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

Selecting for alkali soils

R.S. Rana, Central Soil Salinity Research Institute, Karnal 132001, India

Severely deteriorated alkali soils of the Indo-gangetic plain, are characterized by high pH (usually more than 9.0), sodicity (exchangeable sodium percentage often exceeding 30), calcium carbonate precipitation, Zn deficiency, and poor physical properties. Groundwater is good.

Progress toward combining superior tolerance with good yield potential is slow, largely because of nonavailability of reliable and efficient selection criteria. Selecting directly for grain yield under edaphic stress is limited by low heritability of observed variation and failure to distinguish between yield potential and capacity to cope with specific stress factors.

For indirect selection for yield ability under alkali soil conditions, 30 rice varieties were studied in specially designed 3 m × 3 m × 1 m test plots with 2 alkali soil grades (pH 9.3 and 9.6) and in nonstress productive soil over 3 seasons. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. N, P, K, and Zn were applied at 150, 26, 33, and 9 kg/ha. Irrigation followed a specified schedule.

Heritability of 12 characteristics of rice varieties grown in alkali (sodic) soils, and their correlation with grain yield and alkali stress resistance index.^a Karnal, India.

Characteristic	Heritability	Correlation	
		Grain yield	Alkali stress resistance index
Seed germination percentage	30.64	0.14	0.09
Germination rate index	39.81	0.19	0.27
Seedling growth rate	36.25	0.39	0.41
Foliar damage score	45.07	0.37	0.44
Plant height	38.54	0.28	0.29
Vegetative growth rate index	49.86	0.46	0.48
Biomass yield	64.91	0.67	0.71
Panicle-bearing tillers/plot	29.10	0.30	0.29
Grains/plant (no.)	37.29	0.38	0.32
1000-grain weight	35.47	0.41	0.37
Panicle weight	81.10	0.73	0.79
Harvest index	21.17	0.13	0.11

^an = 720 (30 varieties, 2 alkali soils, 4 replications, 3 yr). 'r' value required for 0.01 level of significance = 0.25.

Because grain yield corresponds to product of biomass or total dry matter production (growth rate × growth duration) and harvest index, correlations of 12 characteristics with grain yield under stress conditions *per se* as well as with the "stress resistance index" (average grain yield under stress in relation to corresponding controls taken as one) were computed and variances and heritability of parameters estimated (see table).

Total biomass and panicle weight correlated highly with grain yield under alkali soil conditions as well as with the stress resistance index. A simultaneous

consideration of correlation coefficients and heritability estimates of different traits showed that indirect selection for grain yield in alkali soils via panicle weight and biological yield (cf. harvest index in case of high productivity environment) was likely to be effective.

The product of a variety's yield response index (computed by dividing the particular variety's grain yield by overall mean yield of all varieties under all stress environments) and its stress resistance index provided a more useful index for measuring varietal ratings (rankings) than either index alone. *∞*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DEEP WATER

A simple technique for measuring internode elongation of deep water rice

R. Thakur and D. HilleRisLambers, IRRI

There are two problems in measuring elongation ability of deep water and floating rice.

Measurement is best some 70 d after broadcast seeding, but this requires fairly deep tanks. But for savings in time and water, most tests are carried out at 30 d after seeding, and in water no more than 100-150 cm deep.

In genetics work, it is essential to do progeny tests on all individuals, including those found unable to

elongate. Plants in the latter category, however, are destroyed in all current tests.

We tested a new approach to elongation testing by forcing test plants in a horizontal position, except for their upper parts.

Six varieties were selected: TCA4, TCA177 (floating rice), Janki (deep